

Covered for Life: Lifelong Area Coverage under Spatiotemporal Uncertainty

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Abstract. To efficiently cover an environment, robots must be able to handle changes in occupancy during execution. These occupancy dynamics are often *stochastic*, and so we cannot deterministically predict when a location will be occupied. Existing coverage solutions either assume static environments or react to changes as they occur, limiting performance. In this paper we present a framework for *lifelong area coverage under spatiotemporal uncertainty*, where a robot repeats coverage over multiple episodes. The stochastic occupancy dynamics are *a priori* unknown and learned using the observations received during coverage. For each coverage episode, we build and solve a partially observable Markov decision process which exploits our learned spatiotemporal dynamics model to improve performance. We demonstrate the efficacy of our framework across extensive experiments in synthetic environments.

1 Introduction

Robot area coverage is crucial for autonomous search and rescue [20], underwater exploration [43], and floor cleaning [4]. Many of these problems feature *dynamic* environments where occupancy changes over time. The spatiotemporal processes which govern occupancy are often *stochastic*, i.e. we can't deterministically predict which locations will be occupied and when. This increases the difficulty of area coverage, as robots can no longer follow a fixed path. In this paper, we address *lifelong area coverage under spatiotemporal uncertainty (LACSTU)*. Here, a mobile robot with limited sensing repeats coverage over multiple episodes in an *a priori* unknown environment while learning the occupancy dynamics.

Example 1. Consider the robot vacuum cleaner in Fig. 1, which cleans a house each day by covering it with its sweepers. Domestic environments change within an episode, i.e. a cleaning run, as people or animals may move through a room; and between episodes, as furniture may move to accommodate guests. The robot does not know these dynamics *a priori*, but can detect obstacles within a limited *field of view (FOV)*.

Coverage planners synthesise collision-free paths for covering an environment [34]. Existing offline planners often assume a static environment model [6], which causes the resulting plans to be invalidated if the environment changes during execution. Online solutions handle dynamic obstacles by making local decisions

Figure 1. A robot vacuum cleaner operating in a domestic environment represented as a grid. White cells are free and black cells are occupied. The robot's FOV is shown in red.

based on current observations [3, 43], or replanning as obstacles are observed [7]. These approaches ignore the long-term occupancy dynamics, which improves computational efficiency but reduces the quality of coverage. For example, some portions of the environment may only be free for a small duration. Therefore, to maximise coverage in dynamic environments we must explicitly capture spatiotemporal uncertainty during planning.

In this paper, we present a framework for LACSTU which decouples planning and learning. We represent the stochastic occupancy dynamics using an *independent Markov chain (iMac)* model learned over multiple coverage episodes [28]. For learning, we update distributions over the iMac parameters after each episode using the observations collected during that episode. For coverage planning, we construct a *partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP)* [10] using the current posterior mean iMac estimate, and solve it online to maximise expected coverage. By explicitly reasoning over our learned model of spatiotemporal uncertainty during planning, we synthesise behaviour which is robust to changes in occupancy. To the best of our knowledge, our approach is the first to address LACSTU.

The primary contributions of this work are (i) a novel formulation of the LACSTU problem; (ii) a POMDP planner for area coverage under spatiotemporal uncertainty; and (iii) a decoupled planning and learning framework for LACSTU. We demonstrate the efficacy of our approach with extensive experiments in synthetic environments.

2 Related Work

Classical coverage planning techniques include wavefront algorithms [42]; travelling salesperson problem (TSP) solvers [4]; and

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boustrophedon-based planners, which move the robot back and forth across the environment [6]. To improve scalability, many methods decompose the environment into disjoint obstacle-free regions, plan a path between regions, and then cover each region separately [1, 6, 16]. However, many of these approaches synthesise paths offline assuming the environment is static. This is unsuitable for LACSTU, as the paths may become blocked once the environment changes during execution. Random planners are also a common coverage approach despite their limited performance [34], and have been used for robot vacuum cleaners due to their low computational overhead [22].

Online coverage planners allow robots to adapt as obstacles are observed. Viet et al. [36] and Khan et al. [11] cover unknown environments by following a boustrophedon motion until all neighbouring locations are occluded or visited. The robot then backtracks, finding the best location to start a new boustrophedon motion. Sadek et al. [29] create small regions based on current sensor data, and cover each region using genetic algorithms. However, these approaches assume the environment is static and thus cannot be used to cover dynamic environments. To mitigate this, Dakulović et al. [7] use D^* [32] to efficiently replan upon detecting unexpected obstacles. However, the space outside the robot’s FOV is assumed to remain static during replanning. This limits coverage performance in highly dynamic environments, as the planning model diverges from what we observe during execution.

Local decision-making techniques can cover dynamic environments without a global planning model. Bormann et al. [3] navigate to an energy minimising location at each timestep, where the energy function considers occupancy within the robot’s FOV, distance, angular rotation, and a term which keeps the robot on boustrophedon-like tracks. Alternatively, Qiu et al. [24], Yan et al. [40], and Zhu et al. [43] represent each location as a neuron in a neural network, and select the location with maximal activation at each timestep. Neuron activations are computed from observations and the activations of neighbouring neurons. By foregoing a planning model, these techniques ignore how and when the environment changes. This produces suboptimal behaviour as a robot may become stuck, or miss the only opportunity to cover a particular location. In this paper, we learn a model of the spatiotemporal occupancy dynamics from the observations collected during coverage. We then exploit this during planning to synthesise behaviour which is robust to occupancy changes, improving performance. Though we plan online, the techniques we present can also be applied offline.

Coverage planning under uncertainty has received limited research attention. Larach et al. [17] construct a Markov decision process (MDP) for coverage which captures action outcome uncertainty in a static environment. Saha et al. [30] formulate area coverage in dynamic environments as an MDP, but only consider dynamic obstacles within the robot’s FOV. Finally, Murtaza et al. [20] capture multi-robot coverage as a POMDP, similar to this paper. However the environment is static, where the POMDP captures uncertainty over the presence of people at different locations. In this paper, we construct and solve a POMDP for area coverage which utilises a learned spatiotemporal model of occupancy uncertainty. This allows us to predict the current occupancy state of every location in the environment, which leads to improved coverage.

Area coverage under uncertainty is similar to exploring an unknown environment. During exploration, a robot maximises information gain to learn the environment state, which often results in the robot covering most of the environment. Exploration is often modelled as a POMDP and solved using sample-based techniques, similar to this paper [12, 18, 21]. The exploration POMDP belief represents the

robot’s uncertain knowledge of the environment, where the reward encourages the robot to reduce belief uncertainty. To explore large environments, Kim et al. [12], Peltzer et al. [23], and Ott et al. [21] plan hierarchically using a coarse global map alongside a high-fidelity local map surrounding the robot. An alternative approach is to use neural networks to predict occupancy outside of the robot’s FOV to guide exploration [8, 25]. Budd et al. [5] explore partially unknown environments while completing robotic missions, where unknown environment features are modelled using a Gaussian process. The above exploration approaches assume the environment is static and so are unsuitable for LACSTU. For lifelong exploration in dynamic environments, Bonnevie et al. [2] guide the robot using a term which considers a location’s rate of change, visitation rate, and whether its current occupancy is known. Similar to this paper, the occupancy dynamics are represented using iMac [28]. However, Bonnevie et al. [2] assume the environment is static during an episode, with changes only occurring between episodes. In this paper, we learn an iMac model which captures how occupancy changes within an episode, and use it to construct and solve a POMDP for area coverage in dynamic environments.

A map of dynamics is a spatiotemporal representation of an environment’s dynamics [15]. iMac represents the dynamics of each cell in a grid as an independent Markov chain [28], and has been extended to capture observation uncertainty [35], human movement [38, 39], and dependencies between cells [19, 37]. We describe iMac further in Sec. 3. FreMEEn captures more complex periodic temporal dynamics using Fourier transforms [13]. This has been extended to represent continuous variables such as the number of people in an area rather than just occupancy [14]. This is achieved by projecting time onto circles representing different periods, such as hours or days. The above representations have been used to support robot planning [2, 31], but to the best of our knowledge have not been used for area coverage. In this paper, we capture stochastic occupancy dynamics using iMac due to its simplicity and applicability to grid-based area coverage [28]. However, our framework can be adapted to use different representations in a straightforward way.

3 Preliminaries

We write $|X|$ to denote the cardinality of a set X , and $\llbracket i, j \rrbracket$ to denote the discrete interval $\{i, \dots, j\}$, $j \geq i$. Further, let $\mathbb{1}[x]$ return 1 if x is true, and 0 otherwise.

Grid Maps. In this paper, we discretise the environment into a 4-connected grid.

Definition 3.1. A 4-connected $X \times Y$ grid map is a tuple $\mathcal{G} = \langle V, \Phi \rangle$, where $V = \llbracket 0, X - 1 \rrbracket \times \llbracket 0, Y - 1 \rrbracket$ is a finite set of cells, and $\Phi : V \rightarrow \{\text{Fr}, \text{Oc}\}$ is an occupancy function, such that $\Phi(v)$ returns Oc if cell $v \in V$ is occupied, and Fr otherwise. From cell v , a robot can navigate directly to any cell in its 4-neighbourhood.

Partially Observable Markov Decision Processes (POMDPs).

POMDPs model partially observable, non-deterministic systems with stochastic outcomes [10]. We use POMDPs to model area coverage under spatiotemporal uncertainty.

Definition 3.2. A POMDP is a tuple $\mathcal{M} = \langle S, A, T, R, Z, O \rangle$, where S and A are finite sets of states and actions; $T : S \times A \times S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a transition function, such that $T(s, a, s')$ is the probability of reaching state s' after executing action a in state s ; and $R : S \times A \times S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is a reward function, where $R(s, a, s')$ is the reward for reaching state s' from state s after executing action

a . Z is a finite set of observations, and $O : Z \times S \times A \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is an observation function, where $O(z, s', a)$ is the probability of observing z in state s' after executing action a .

As the underlying state of a POMDP is not observable, we maintain a *belief* over the state space at each timestep.

Definition 3.3. A *belief* $b : S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a distribution over POMDP states, where $b(s)$ is the probability of residing in state $s \in S$. The initial belief is denoted \bar{b} , and the space of beliefs is denoted B .

After executing an action $a \in A$, the robot receives an observation $z \in Z$. With this, we compute a posterior belief b' from our prior belief b by applying Bayes rule:

$$b'(s') = \eta \cdot O(z, s', a) \cdot \sum_{s \in S} T(s, a, s') \cdot b(s), \quad (1)$$

where η is a normalisation constant. Finally, we define policies over robot behaviour.

Definition 3.4. A *policy* is a mapping $\pi : B \rightarrow A$, where $\pi(b)$ defines the action to execute under belief b .

Independent Markov Chain (iMac) Map of Dynamics. iMac is a spatiotemporal representation of occupancy dynamics for grid maps [28]. We learn an iMac model over multiple episodes to support coverage. iMac models the dynamics of each grid cell independently as a two-state *discrete-time Markov chain (DTMC)*.

Definition 3.5. A *DTMC* for cell $v \in V$ is a tuple $\mathcal{C}_v = \langle S, p^{\text{init}}, p^{\text{entry}}, p^{\text{exit}}, T \rangle$, where $S = \{\text{Fr}, \text{Oc}\}$ is a set of states which represent v being free or occupied, and p^{init} is the initial probability of v being occupied. p^{entry} and p^{exit} are the probabilities of v switching from free to occupied or occupied to free within a single timestep respectively. With this, transition function $T : S \times S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ captures the probability of v switching states between timesteps:

$$T(s, s') = \begin{cases} p^{\text{entry}} & s = \text{Fr} \text{ and } s' = \text{Oc} \\ 1 - p^{\text{entry}} & s = \text{Fr} \text{ and } s' = \text{Fr} \\ p^{\text{exit}} & s = \text{Oc} \text{ and } s' = \text{Fr} \\ 1 - p^{\text{exit}} & s = \text{Oc} \text{ and } s' = \text{Oc}. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In this paper, subscripts denote an element belonging to a model, e.g. T_v is the transition function for DTMC \mathcal{C}_v , and $\Phi_{\mathcal{G}}$ is the occupancy function of grid map \mathcal{G} . As the dynamics of each cell are treated as independent, the complete iMac model is the set of DTMCs.

Definition 3.6. An *iMac* model \mathcal{I} for a grid map \mathcal{G} is a set of DTMCs, one for each cell, i.e. $\mathcal{I} = \bigcup_{v \in V} \{\mathcal{C}_v\}$.

To accurately capture the dynamics for cell $v \in V$, Saarinen et al. [28] learn p_v^{init} , p_v^{entry} , and p_v^{exit} from data using Bayesian estimation. To demonstrate, consider p_v^{entry} , which is the p value of a Bernoulli distribution with a beta conjugate prior $\text{Beta}(\alpha_v^{\text{entry}}, \beta_v^{\text{entry}})$. Here, α_v^{entry} is the number of positive observations in the data, i.e. when cell v switches from free to occupied, and β_v^{entry} is the number of negative observations, i.e. when v remains free between two timesteps. p_v^{entry} is then estimated as the mean of the beta distribution:

$$p_v^{\text{entry}} = \mathbb{E}[\text{Beta}(\alpha_v^{\text{entry}}, \beta_v^{\text{entry}})] = \frac{\alpha_v^{\text{entry}}}{\alpha_v^{\text{entry}} + \beta_v^{\text{entry}}}. \quad (3)$$

This process is analogous for p_v^{init} and p_v^{exit} . In Sec. 5, we update the beta distributions after each episode using robot observations.

4 Problem Formulation

In this section, we formulate LACSTU. We begin by defining our assumptions over the environment and robot.

Definition 4.1. Let \mathcal{G}^t be the grid map at time t . A *stochastic dynamics model* \mathcal{D} dictates grid occupancy at each timestep. Under \mathcal{D} , the occupancy function $\Phi_{\mathcal{G}^{t+1}}$ at time $t+1$ may differ from $\Phi_{\mathcal{G}^t}$, but the cell set is unchanged, i.e. $V_{\mathcal{G}^t} = V_{\mathcal{G}^{t+1}}$.

We denote the true dynamics model with \mathcal{D}_{GT} , which we assume remains constant across episodes. We use a holonomic robot which at each timestep can navigate to an adjacent cell or wait at its current cell, where navigation always succeeds. Further, the robot has a sensor for detecting occupancy.

Definition 4.2. The robot's *FOV* is given by a function $\text{FOV} : V \rightarrow 2^V$, where $\text{FOV}(v)$ describes the cells observable from cell $v \in V$.

Definition 4.3. Let $v \in V$ be the robot's current cell. At each timestep, the robot makes an *observation* $z : V \rightarrow \{\text{Fr}, \text{Oc}, ?\}$ which captures occupancy within its FOV. Here, $z(v') = \text{Fr}$ or Oc if $v' \in \text{FOV}(v)$ and ? otherwise, where ? represents unknown occupancy outside the FOV.

To simplify notation, we assume robot observations are deterministic. However, our approach can be extended to handle stochastic observations in a straightforward way. We now define the notion of coverage, which the robot maximises during planning.

Definition 4.4. Let \bar{v} be the robot's initial cell. The *expected coverage* $\text{COV}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\bar{v}, H}(\pi)$ of a policy π under dynamics model \mathcal{D} is the expected number of grid cells covered by the robot up to time H .

Next, we formulate the area coverage problem under spatiotemporal uncertainty, i.e. the planning portion of LACSTU.

Problem 1 (Area Coverage). Given a dynamics model \mathcal{D} and initial cell $\bar{v} \in V$, synthesise a policy $\pi_{\mathcal{D}}^*$ which maximises expected coverage up to the planning horizon H , i.e.:

$$\pi_{\mathcal{D}}^* = \underset{\pi}{\text{argmax}} \text{COV}_{\mathcal{D}}^{\bar{v}, H}(\pi). \quad (4)$$

To maximise coverage, we must solve the area coverage problem for the true dynamics model \mathcal{D}_{GT} . However, \mathcal{D}_{GT} is *a priori* unknown and must be learned over multiple episodes; this is the LACSTU problem. We formulate LACSTU in terms of *regret*, i.e. the difference in expected coverage between an optimal policy for the learned model versus the ground truth model. Here, the expected coverage of both policies is computed under \mathcal{D}_{GT} , which is representative of the real environment.

Problem 2 (LACSTU). Consider a robot that repeats area coverage over multiple episodes. For each episode, the robot starts at cell $\bar{v} \in V$ and finishes at time H . Learn a dynamics model \mathcal{D}^* such that the optimal policy for \mathcal{D}^* minimises regret, i.e.:

$$\mathcal{D}^* = \underset{\mathcal{D}}{\text{argmin}} \text{regret}^{\bar{v}, H}(\pi_{\mathcal{D}}^*) \quad (5)$$

$$= \underset{\mathcal{D}}{\text{argmin}} \text{COV}_{\mathcal{D}_{GT}}^{\bar{v}, H}(\pi_{\mathcal{D}_{GT}}^*) - \text{COV}_{\mathcal{D}_{GT}}^{\bar{v}, H}(\pi_{\mathcal{D}}^*). \quad (6)$$

Figure 2. An overview of the LACSTU framework. In each episode, we build and solve a coverage POMDP using the posterior mean iMac model. Robot observations are used to update the POMDP belief and the beta distributions for each iMac parameter.

5 Solution Approach

LACSTU can be formulated exactly as a Bayes-adaptive POMDP (BA-POMDP) [27]. Here, a POMDP with *a priori* unknown transition dynamics is augmented to capture the posterior over the transition function at each state. BA-POMDP solutions efficiently trade between exploration to improve the transition model, and exploiting the current model to maximise reward. However, exact BA-POMDP solvers are intractable for realistic problems due to the number of possible posteriors [9]. Therefore, in Fig. 2 we present a decoupled framework for planning and learning. Our framework approximates the true dynamics model \mathcal{D}_{GT} by learning an iMac model \mathcal{I} . We maintain distributions over the iMac parameters, and use the distribution means to construct an iMac model at the start of each episode. From this, we build and solve a POMDP \mathcal{M} for area coverage online which explicitly captures the occupancy dynamics in the current iMac model. During coverage, the robot receives observations which are used to update the POMDP belief at each timestep and the iMac parameter distributions at the end of each episode. We proceed by describing the learning and planning components of our framework in detail.

Learning. To learn an iMac model \mathcal{I} , we maintain beta distributions over p_v^{init} , p_v^{entry} , and p_v^{exit} for each cell $v \in V$, as described in Sec. 3. We initialise the α and β values for each beta distribution to 1. After each episode, we update the beta posteriors using the robot observations received during coverage. Formally, let z^t be the observation at time t , $t \in \llbracket 0, H \rrbracket$. For cell $v \in V$, the posterior over p_v^{init} is updated using z^0 , and the posteriors over p_v^{entry} and p_v^{exit} are updated using the occupancy changes between observations, i.e.:

$$\alpha_v^{\text{init}} += \mathbb{1}[z^0(v) = \text{Oc}], \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_v^{\text{init}} += \mathbb{1}[z^0(v) = \text{Fr}], \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_v^{\text{entry}} += \sum_{t=0}^{H-1} \mathbb{1}[z^t(v) = \text{Fr} \text{ and } z^{t+1}(v) = \text{Oc}], \quad (9)$$

$$\beta_v^{\text{entry}} += \sum_{t=0}^{H-1} \mathbb{1}[z^t(v) = \text{Fr} \text{ and } z^{t+1}(v) = \text{Fr}], \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha_v^{\text{exit}} += \sum_{t=0}^{H-1} \mathbb{1}[z^t(v) = \text{Oc} \text{ and } z^{t+1}(v) = \text{Fr}], \quad (11)$$

$$\beta_v^{\text{exit}} += \sum_{t=0}^{H-1} \mathbb{1}[z^t(v) = \text{Oc} \text{ and } z^{t+1}(v) = \text{Oc}]. \quad (12)$$

At the start of each episode we construct an iMac model from the beta posterior means (see Eq. 3). This allows us to exploit our learned model to improve area coverage, which we discuss next. However, as

a result the robot will never explore to improve its model [33]. Despite this, in Sec. 6 we show that this does not affect the speed of learning.

By using iMac to represent occupancy dynamics we ignore spatial dependencies between cells. Spatial dependencies could be hard-coded, such as in [19, 37], or learned. However, hard-coded dependencies may introduce modelling inaccuracies similar to our independence assumption, and dependency learning requires a large dataset which records complete map occupancy at each timestep, which is difficult to collect using a robot with a limited FOV.

Planning. For each episode, we solve area coverage by building and solving a POMDP \mathcal{M} from the posterior mean iMac model \mathcal{I} which explicitly models stochastic occupancy dynamics. In \mathcal{M} , the robot fully observes its current cell, the time, and the cells it has covered, but maintains a belief over the current grid occupancy, which is partially observable. After each action, the grid map evolves stochastically according to iMac model \mathcal{I} .

Definition 5.1. Given iMac model \mathcal{I} , planning horizon H , and FOV FOV , a *coverage POMDP* is a tuple $\mathcal{M} = \langle S_{\mathcal{M}}, A_{\mathcal{M}}, T_{\mathcal{M}}, R_{\mathcal{M}}, Z_{\mathcal{M}}, O_{\mathcal{M}} \rangle$, where $S_{\mathcal{M}} = V \times \llbracket 0, H \rrbracket \times \mathbb{G} \times 2^V$, with \mathbb{G} being the set of grid maps. A state $s \in S_{\mathcal{M}}$ contains the robot’s current cell, the timestep, the current grid map, and the set of covered cells. The action set $A_{\mathcal{M}} = \{\text{up}, \text{down}, \text{left}, \text{right}, \text{wait}\}$, i.e. the robot can move to an adjacent cell or wait.

Before defining the transition function $T_{\mathcal{M}}$, we require additional notation. Let $\text{trg}(v, a)$ be the target cell after executing action $a \in A_{\mathcal{M}}$ in cell $v \in V$, assuming it is free. For example, $\text{trg}((2, 3), \text{up}) = (2, 2)$. If the robot tries to navigate outside the map, it remains in its current cell. Further, we define a function $T_{\mathcal{I}} : \mathbb{G} \times \mathbb{G} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, where $T_{\mathcal{I}}(\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{G}')$ is the probability of transitioning between grid maps \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{G}' under iMac model \mathcal{I} , with $V_{\mathcal{G}} = V_{\mathcal{G}'}$ as per Def. 4.1:

$$T_{\mathcal{I}}(\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{G}') = \prod_{v \in V_{\mathcal{G}}} T_v(\Phi_{\mathcal{G}}(v), \Phi_{\mathcal{G}'}(v)). \quad (13)$$

The transition function $T_{\mathcal{M}}$ captures the occupancy dynamics and how they affect robot actions. After executing action a in cell v , the grid map is updated according to iMac model \mathcal{I} , the timestep is increased, and the coverage set is updated with the successor cell. If the target cell $\text{trg}(v, a)$ is free in the successor state, navigation succeeds and the robot reaches the target. However, if $\text{trg}(v, a)$ is occupied, navigation fails and the robot stays in v , which remains free. From timestep H , there are no further transitions. Formally, for states

$s = (v, t, \mathcal{G}, c)$ and $s' = (v', t', \mathcal{G}', c')$:

$$T_{\mathcal{M}}(s, a, s') = \begin{cases} T_{\mathcal{I}}(\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{G}') & v' = \text{trg}(v, a), \\ & t' = t + 1, t < H, \\ & \Phi_{\mathcal{G}'}(v') = \text{Fr} \text{ and} \\ & c' = c \cup \{v'\} \\ \frac{T_{\mathcal{I}}(\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{G}')}{T_v(\text{Fr}, \text{Fr})} & v' = v, \\ & t' = t + 1, t < H, \\ & \text{OcOrWait}, \\ & \Phi_{\mathcal{G}'}(v') = \text{Fr} \text{ and} \\ & c' = c \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where `OcOrWait` holds if $\Phi_{\mathcal{G}'}(\text{trg}(v, a)) = \text{Oc}$ or $a = \text{wait}$, i.e. the target is blocked or the robot is waiting.

The reward function $R_{\mathcal{M}}$ returns one when the robot covers a new cell, and zero otherwise. Formally, for states $s = (v, t, \mathcal{G}, c)$ and $s' = (v', t', \mathcal{G}', c')$:

$$R_{\mathcal{M}}(s, a, s') = |c' \setminus c|. \quad (15)$$

The observation set $Z_{\mathcal{M}} = V \rightarrow \{\text{Fr}, \text{Oc}, ?\}$, i.e. an observation is a function which defines occupancy within the robot's FOV, as per Def. 4.3. As observations are deterministic, the observation function $O_{\mathcal{M}}$ returns one if the observation matches the grid occupancy in the POMDP state, and zero otherwise. Formally, for state $s = (v, t, \mathcal{G}, c)$:

$$O_{\mathcal{M}}(z, s', a) = \prod_{v \in \text{FOV}(v')} \mathbb{1}[z(v) = \Phi_{\mathcal{G}'}(v)] \cdot \prod_{v \notin \text{FOV}(v')} \mathbb{1}[z(v) = ?]. \quad (16)$$

During area coverage, the robot maintains a belief over grid occupancy, which is updated using Eq. 1. For coverage POMDPs, this requires rolling the prior belief forward one step under the iMac model and current observation.

Definition 5.2. Given iMac model \mathcal{I} , initial cell \bar{v} , and initial observation z^0 , the *initial belief* $\bar{b}_{\mathcal{M}}$ for coverage POMDP \mathcal{M} captures the initial grid occupancy, where \bar{v} is free, and cells in $\text{FOV}(\bar{v})$ match z^0 . Formally, for state $s = (v, t, \mathcal{G}, c)$:

$$\bar{b}_{\mathcal{M}}(s) = \begin{cases} \prod_{v \neq \bar{v}} p_v^{\text{init}} & v = \bar{v}, t = 0, \Phi_{\mathcal{G}}(\bar{v}) = \text{Fr}, \\ & O_{\mathcal{M}}(z^0, s, \cdot) = 1 \text{ and } c = \{\bar{v}\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Example 2. Consider the POMDP in Fig. 3. Assume the robot starts in state s_1 , i.e. cell (0, 1) at time $t = 0$, where only (1, 0) is occupied. If the robot navigates right and succeeds, it reaches (1, 1) at time $t = 1$, e.g. state s_2 , and receives a reward for covering (1, 1). If navigation fails, it remains in (0, 1) at time $t = 1$, e.g. state s_3 , and receives no reward. The transition function captures the occupancy dynamics, e.g. $T_{\mathcal{M}}(s_1, \text{right}, s_2) = p_{(0,0)}^{\text{entry}} \cdot p_{(1,0)}^{\text{exit}} \cdot p_{(0,1)}^{\text{entry}} \cdot (1 - p_{(1,1)}^{\text{entry}})$, as all cells except (1, 1) change their occupancy.

The worst-case space complexity of a coverage POMDP \mathcal{M} is $\mathcal{O}(|V| \cdot (H + 1) \cdot 2^{|V|} \cdot 2^{|V|})$. Here, $|V|$ is the number of cells, $(H + 1)$ is the number of timesteps, and the $2^{|V|}$ terms capture the number of possible grid maps and coverage sets respectively. The exponential increase in the grid size limits scalability. Despite this, our planner still scales up to 8×8 grids, as demonstrated in Sec. 6.

In this paper, we solve coverage POMDPs online due to their exponential scalability [26]. At each timestep, the robot plans under its current belief to synthesise the next action. Following action execution, the robot receives an observation z which is used to update its belief b . Any online POMDP solver can be used here, however we use DESPOT, a state-of-the-art anytime sample-based solver [41]. DESPOT avoids enumerating the POMDP by searching through a sparse, sample-based approximation of the POMDP belief tree. As planning time is limited, we often synthesise suboptimal behaviour. Despite this, our approach provides efficient coverage, which we demonstrate in Sec. 6.

Figure 3. A coverage POMDP for a 2×2 grid map. White cells are free, black cells are occupied, and green ticks indicate covered cells.

6 Experiments

In this section we evaluate our LACSTU framework in terms of planning performance, learning speed, and the effects of learning on planning. All experiments are run on Ubuntu 22.04 with an AMD Ryzen 7 5825u CPU and 40GB of RAM. All software is implemented in C++.

Problem Setup. For all experimental problems, the robot begins in cell (0, 0), and the planning horizon $H = \lceil 1.3 \cdot |V| \rceil$. An empty grid can be covered in $|V|$ steps, and so increasing H beyond $|V|$ allows for backtracking to handle dynamic obstacles.

Experimental Environments. We consider grid maps of size 6×6 , 7×7 , 8×8 , and 10×10 . For each grid map, we randomly generate an iMac model where 10% of cells change rapidly, i.e. $p^{\text{init}}, p^{\text{entry}},$ and $p^{\text{exit}} = 0.5$; 20% change slowly, i.e. $p^{\text{init}} = 0.5$, and $p^{\text{entry}}, p^{\text{exit}} = 0.05$; 30% are between the fast and slow cells, i.e. $p^{\text{init}} = 0.5$, and $p^{\text{entry}}, p^{\text{exit}} = 0.2$; and 40% of cells are permanently free, i.e. $p^{\text{init}}, p^{\text{entry}} = 0$, and $p^{\text{exit}} = 1$. To generate more realistic iMac models, we perturb the parameters for all dynamic cells by a value sampled from $\mathcal{U}(-0.01, 0.01)$. iMac models with multiple levels of dynamics are more representative of real-world problems. For example, in Example 1 furniture moves less frequently than a dog walks through a room. For all maps, $p_{(0,0)}^{\text{init}} = 0$, i.e. the robot's initial cell is always free at $t = 0$.

POMDP Solver. For online POMDP planning, we use the DESPOT implementation provided by Ye et al. [41]¹. To improve search, DESPOT requires bounds on the expected value from a POMDP state, i.e. the expected coverage. Recall that one cell can be covered per timestep. For state $s = (v, t, \mathcal{G}, c)$, the upper bound is

¹ <https://github.com/AdaCompNUS/despot>

Figure 4. The planning performance for each method under the true iMac model.

Figure 5. The learning error in the iMac model over time. The confidence bounds show one standard deviation.

$\min(|V| - |c|, H - t)$, i.e. the remaining cells to cover or the time remaining, whichever is lower. The lower bound is represented with a greedy policy which navigates to the uncovered neighbour that is most likely to be free in the next timestep, according to the iMac model. If all neighbours are covered, a random action is selected. We instantiate DESPOT as follows: the search depth, simulation length, and rollout length are set to H , i.e. we search up to the planning horizon. As we solve finite horizon problems, the discount factor is 1. The DESPOT tree is constructed from 500 sampled scenarios and the target uncertainty gap is 0.95, as in Ye et al. [41]. We set the regularisation constant to 0.1 based on preliminary results. The robot plans for 1 second per timestep. If exceeded, DESPOT waits for the current trial to finish before terminating.

Evaluating Planning Performance. In this experiment, we evaluate our POMDP coverage planner against five baselines:

- *Greedy*: The greedy policy we use as a lower bound for DESPOT. This baseline exploits the dynamics model without any long-term planning.
- *Random*: A random coverage policy. Despite its simplicity, this is a common coverage approach [34].
- *Energy functional* [3]: At each timestep, the robot selects the free, uncovered neighbour which minimises an energy function. If all neighbours are covered or occupied, the robot moves towards the uncovered cell which minimises the energy function over the rest of the map. We adjust the original energy function to handle 4-connected grids rather than 8, and remove the rotation cost, as we use holonomic robots. This approach outperforms other local decision-making techniques for area coverage [4].
- *Online boustrophedon* [36]: At each timestep, the robot selects a free, uncovered neighbour using the priority order up, down, left, and right. If all neighbours are covered or occupied, the robot waits.
- *Offline boustrophedon*: The robot synthesises a boustrophedon path offline assuming an empty environment, i.e. a path which covers the grid by moving back and forth. If a target cell becomes occupied

during execution, the robot waits until it is free. Boustrophedon methods are a classical coverage technique, and the above two baselines present two contrasting approaches for handling obstacles: wait for them to clear, or change direction.

Using the iMac models, we sample 40 episodes of dynamics for the 6×6 , 7×7 , and 8×8 maps. We run each method on the sampled episodes, and measure the proportion of cells covered within horizon H . All methods can access the true dynamics model, though only our approach and the greedy baseline use it. We present the results for each grid map in Fig. 4.

In each grid map, the POMDP planner statistically significantly outperforms all baselines, according to a one-sided Mann-Whitney U test with $p = 0.05$. In Fig. 4, the random baseline covers the fewest cells. This baseline has no notion of coverage, and can easily get stuck in small areas, particularly in cluttered maps. Both boustrophedon baselines also perform poorly. Under the offline boustrophedon method the robot becomes blocked if it reaches an occupied cell with slow dynamics. The online boustrophedon method mitigates this by changing direction upon reaching an occupied cell. However, this may cause the robot to miss a large portion of the environment, and if the occupied cell changes rapidly, waiting may have been a better option. This demonstrates the need to reason over occupancy dynamics during planning.

The greedy and energy functional baselines perform similarly, though the energy functional method has slightly higher medians. The greedy baseline reasons over stochastic occupancy dynamics myopically, limiting performance. The energy functional approach ignores occupancy dynamics, but backtracks to fill in coverage holes once all neighbours are covered. These holes may be far away, producing less myopic behaviour than the other baselines and improving coverage.

In summary, our POMDP planner outperforms the baselines by reasoning over stochastic occupancy dynamics up to the planning horizon. However, DESPOT struggles to complete trials within the allotted planning time for maps larger than 8×8 . In this instance, the greedy or energy functional methods may provide an acceptable alternative.

Evaluating the Speed of Learning. Next, we evaluate how quickly our framework learns the true iMac model. We compare our learning approach to posterior sampling, which samples from the beta posteriors at the start of each episode instead of taking the posterior means [33]. This encourages exploration if the beta posterior is uncertain. We sample 40 sets of 200 episodes for the 10×10 grid map. For each set of episodes and method, we first initialise the iMac beta distributions, and then update them after each episode. For scalability, we use the greedy baseline for coverage, which still exploits the iMac model. After each episode, we measure the learning error as the sum

Figure 6. The planning performance as the learned iMac model improves.

of absolute errors between the true iMac model parameters and the current posterior mean estimates, regardless of method. We present the learning results in Fig. 5. Note that the iMac learning error will never reach zero as some parameters are unobservable. For example, the robot will never observe the initial occupancy of any cell outside of its initial FOV, or p^{exit} for any permanently free cell, as the cell is never occupied.

The posterior mean and posterior sampling methods both converge within 100 episodes, though most of the learning occurs within the first 10-15. We investigate the quality of the learned model in terms of planning performance in the next experiment. The posterior mean and posterior sampling approaches also produce near identical learning curves, which suggests that robot exploration does not improve the speed of learning. This is likely due to the nature of area coverage and the simplicity of iMac. During area coverage the robot should visit each cell, and so most cells will be observed multiple times per episode aside from any additional exploration. Moreover, iMac is Markovian, i.e. the probability of a cell being occupied at the next timestep is only dependent on its current occupancy. With this, we gain similar information irrespective of when we observe a cell, and so the observations made during coverage are sufficient for learning. Exploration may become beneficial if we used a more complex spatiotemporal dynamics model such as FreMEn [13], where occupancy is dependent on time. Here, exploration could be used to guide the robot towards an area at a time where our occupancy model is highly uncertain.

Evaluating the Effects of Learning on Planning. To validate the full LACSTU framework, we evaluate how planning performance changes as we learn the iMac model. For this, we complete 150 randomly generated training episodes in the 6×6 , 7×7 , and 8×8 grid maps starting from an initialised set of beta distributions. We then take the posterior mean iMac model prior to the first episode, and after episodes 1, 5, 10, 50, 100, and 150. We evaluate each iMac model by using it in the POMDP planner for each of the 40 sampled test episodes used in the planning experiment. We also do this for the true iMac model. As in the planning experiment, we measure the proportion of cells covered within the planning horizon. We present the results for each grid map in Fig. 6.

In each of the three grid maps, model learning improves area coverage. Our learned model produces statistically similar planning performance to the true dynamics model by episode 5 for the 6×6 and 7×7 maps, and by episode 10 for the 8×8 map, according to a two-sided Mann-Whitney U test with $p = 0.05$. These results corroborate the high speed of learning in the previous experiment. The initial iMac model fails to capture the occupancy dynamics, and so planning with it produces the lowest coverage. However, the initial model achieves full coverage in one episode on the 6×6 map,

which no other model achieves. A single episode is unrepresentative of the true dynamics model as a whole and may be better represented using the initial model, though this doesn't generalise. Further, the DESPOT search tree may be constructed from samples which closely match that episode's dynamics. The high speed of learning suggests that our approach may extend to non-stationary dynamics models. Non-stationarity appears in many domains, such as Example 1, where furniture may be moved semi-permanently after a room is redecorated, for example. We will investigate this in future work. For example, we could apply the recency weighting technique in [28], where more recent observations are prioritised during beta posterior updates.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented a decoupled planning and learning framework for LACSTU which explicitly captures spatiotemporal occupancy dynamics. We learn an iMac model of dynamics over multiple episodes, and use the current iMac estimate to build and solve a POMDP for each episode. The behaviour we synthesise is robust to changes in occupancy, resulting in efficient coverage. To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first to address LACSTU. In future work, we will consider hierarchical coverage planning to improve scalability. This will allow us to analyse the impact of different FOVs on coverage. We will also investigate how semantic information about obstacles can inform model learning. Further, we will adapt our framework for continuous environments and more complex robot behaviours such as edge following or charger docking. Finally, we will deploy our framework on a real robot.

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